

Kinetics and mechanism of catalysed and uncatalysed oxidation of D-glucose by N-bromosuccinimide in aqueous acidic medium

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of D-glucose by N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in presence of sulphuric acid, KCl, mercuric acetate and acetic acid have been investigated. The observed rate of oxidation is first order with respect to oxidant [NBS] both in the presence and absence of catalysts. A decrease in the dielectric constant of medium decreases the rate. Addition of succinimide [SA], has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. Increase in $[H^+]$ retards the reaction rate. Activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : D-Glucose, N-bromosuccinimide, catalysed reaction, oxidation.

Literature survey reveals that kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of sugar¹ have been carried out using various N-halocompound². The utility of N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) as an oxidising agent and analytical reagent has been reviewed. In this paper we present the results on the catalysed and uncatalysed oxidation of glucose by NBS. Ru^{III}, Ru^{VIII}, Ir^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} have widely been used as homogeneous catalysts in various redox reaction³.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of glucose by NBS in absence of $[Hg(OAc)_2]$ is complicated by parallel bromine oxidation. The results are summarised in Table 1. However bromine oxidation is prevented by using $[Hg(OAc)_2]$. Under the experimental conditions $[NBS] \ll [S]$ (where S denotes the substrate) and in the presence and absence of catalyst the plot of $\log(a-x)$ versus time were linear passing through the origin indicating the order in [NBS] to be unity for both uncatalysed and catalysed systems. The pseudo-first order rate constant does not change with increase in initial concentration of oxidant. The plot of $\log[\text{rate}]$ versus $\log[S]$ in the absence of catalyst was linear with unit slope indicating first order dependence on [S] with increased catalyst [glucose] has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating a fractional order dependence of rate on [glucose] (Table 2). A plot of $\log[\text{rate}]$ vs $\log[\text{glucose}]$ is linear with unit slope. The rate increases with $[Li^+]$, $[Ag^+]$, $[Ru^{III}]$, $[Ir^{III}]$. Mercuric chloride $[HgCl_2]$ had negligible effect on the rate of reaction. An increase in $[H_2SO_4]$ lead to a decrease in the pseudo-first order rate constant $[k']$ and the plot of $[k']$ versus $[H_2SO_4]$ were linear both in catalysed and uncatalysed reaction (Table 3). $NaHSO_4$, succinimide, KCl

have little effect on rate. Rate decreases with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The oxidation of glucose was studied at different temperature (313–328 K). Keeping other experimental conditions same. The Arrhenius plot of k' vs $1/T$ is linear. The activation parameters are given in Table 4.

The rate of reaction decreases with increase in $[H^+]$. The aqueous solution of sugar is an equilibrium mixture of α and β sugars. The $c-1$ of the α -sugar has a hydrogen atom equatorial (hydroxy group in axial position) and direct hydride ion transfer is possible. Further NBS is known to oxidise axial hydroxy group rapidly than equatorial one through hydride ion transfer. So the α -sugars may be more readily oxidised than β -sugars by NBS. Decrease in rate of oxidation with increase in $[H^+]$ also supports that α -sugar and unprotonated NBS are the reactive species in the present study. NBS is known to exist in acidic media in the following equilibria.

Negative effect of $[H^+]$ on the reaction rate observed here does not allow us to assume either of Br^+ or $(H_2OBr)^+$ or HOBr as oxidizing species. So the retarding effect of $[H^+]$ on the rate rules out the possibility of $>N^+HBr$ as the reactive species of NBS. The observed first order dependence on [NBS] as well as [S] in the uncatalysed reaction is suggestive of a mechanism shown in Scheme 1 (α -D-glucose has been taken of a typical example).

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (1)

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k'' [\text{NBS}] [\text{S}]$$

$$\text{or } -\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k''[\text{NBS}] [\text{S}]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}$$

which is complete accord with the observations eq. (1) may be written as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} \times \frac{1}{[\text{NBS}]} = k' = \frac{k''[\text{S}]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}$$

Taking reciprocal as eq. (2) we get,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k''[\text{S}]} + \frac{K[\text{H}^+]}{k''[\text{S}]}$$

where, k' = observed pseudo-first order rate constant, K = equilibrium constant and k'' = constant for uncatalysed reaction.

In order to find out the nature of reactive species, the solvent effect was studied with varying acetic acid concentration in the solvent. The retardation of rate by added acetic acid (+ve dielectric effect) indicate anion dipole or dipole-dipole type of reaction in agreement with the Kirkwood's theory.

First order dependence in [NBS], fractional order each in [S] and [Ru^{III}] and the ability of the platinum group metals to form complexes with organic substrates and highly enhanced rates substantiate the formation of Ru^{III}-S complex (Scheme 2) which slowly reacts with NBS in rate determining step to give products.

Scheme 2

Scheme 2 leads to rate law (3)

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k [\text{NBS}] [\text{complex}] \tag{3}$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1 [\text{NBS}] [\text{S}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{\{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} \{1 + K[\text{H}^+]\}}$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} \times \frac{1}{[\text{NBS}]} = k' = \frac{kK_1 [\text{S}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{\{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} \{1 + K[\text{H}^+]\}} \tag{4}$$

where k' is the pseudo-first order rate constant, k the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step and K_1 the formation constant. Eq. (1) explains all the experimental observations obtained.

Taking reciprocal of eq. (4) we get.

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} \left\{ \frac{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}{kK_1 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \right\} + \frac{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}{k [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \tag{5}$$

It is clear from eq. (5) that the plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{S}]$ at fixed [Ru^{III}] should be linear.

Table 1. Effect of variation [substrate] on rate constant

10^3 [NBS] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^2 [H₂SO₄] = 2.00 mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 5% (v/v); Temp. = 308 K

10^2 [Glucose] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^{-4} \times 1/k'$ (s)	$10^4 \times k'$ (s ⁻¹)	$k'_1 \times 10^3$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
2.0	0.56	1.78	8.90
3.0	0.48	2.08	6.93
4.0	0.45	2.21	5.52
5.0	0.33	3.03	6.06
6.0	0.27	3.75	6.25

First order dependence in [NBS] fractional order each in [S] and [Ir^{III}] and the ability of the platinum group metals to form complexes with organic substrate and highly enhanced rates substantiate the formation of Ir^{III}-S complex (Scheme 3) which slowly reacts with NBS in rate determining step to give products. Negative effect of chloride ions on the reaction rate suggests that equilibrium is favoured to right side in acidic solution of Ir^{III} chloride,

Therefore it may, therefore be assumed that $[\text{IrCl}_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ is the active species of iridium(III) chloride.

On the basis of above statement and observed kinetic data, a probable mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of D-glucose which have been designated as S in the scheme.

Scheme 3

Scheme 3 leads to rate law (6)

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k [\text{NBS}] [\text{complex}] \quad (6)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1[\text{NBS}][\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{\{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} \{1 + K[\text{H}^+]\}}$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} \times \frac{1}{[\text{NBS}]} = k' = \frac{kK_1[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{\{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} \{1 + K[\text{H}^+]\}} \quad (7)$$

where, k' = pseudo-first order rate constant, k = bimolecular rate constant for the slow step, K_1 = formation constant, K = equilibrium constant.

Eq. (7) explains all the experimental observation obtained.

Taking reciprocal of eq. (7) we get,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} \left\{ \frac{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}{kK_1[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]} \right\} + \frac{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}{k[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (8)$$

It is clear from eq. (8) that the plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{S}]$ at fixed $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ should be linear.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [substrate] on rate constant

10^3 [NBS] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^4 [Hg(OAc)₂] = 10.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^3 [KCl] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^2 [H₂SO₄] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 20% (v/v), 10^6 [RuCl₃] = 4.80 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

10^2 [Substrate] (mol dm ⁻³)	$2 + \log k$	$10^4 \times k'$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^{-4} \times 1/k'$ (s)	$4 + \log k'$
2.0	0.32	2.19	0.34	0.4643
3.0	0.50	3.62	0.28	0.5591
4.0	0.62	4.04	0.25	0.6068
5.0	0.72	4.38	0.23	0.6419
6.0	0.80	4.75	0.21	0.6771

Table 3. Effect of variation of [H₂SO₄] on rate constant

[A] 10^3 [NBS] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^4 [Hg(OAc)₂] = 10.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^3 [KCl] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 15% (v/v), 10^2 [glucose] = 5.00 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

[B] 10^3 [NBS] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^4 [Hg(OAc)₂] = 10.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^3 [KCl] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³, 10^2 [glucose] = 3.00 mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 20% (v/v), 10^6 [RuCl₃] = 4.80 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

Uncatalysed [A]		Catalysed [B]	
10^2 [H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 \times k'$ (s ⁻¹)	10^2 [H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 \times k'$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	1.15	1.0	5.15
1.5	0.80	2.0	4.37
2.0	0.65	3.0	3.62
3.0	0.50	5.0	2.60
4.0	0.38	7.0	2.10
6.0	0.26	11.0	1.45

Experimental

Requisite volume (90 cm³) of all reagents, including substrate, were introduced into a reaction vessel and thermally equilibrated to 40 °C. A measured volume (10 cm³) of NBS solution, also at 40 °C was rapidly poured into the reaction vessel. The kinetics were followed by estimating aliquots of the reaction mixture for NBS iodometrically, using starch indicator⁴.

Table 4. Kinetics and thermodynamic parameters for catalysed and uncatalysed reaction

	[Ru ^{III}] catalysed	Uncatalysed	[Ir ^{III}] catalysed
Temp. coefficient	2.01	2.70	2.00
E_a^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	58.92	83.50	58.48
ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	56.40	80.91	55.88
ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	60.09	98.7	59.50
ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-11.78	-56.9	-11.5

Doubly recrystallised sugars (E. Merck) were used for the kinetic studies. NBS solution was always made up and stored in black coated flask to prevent photochemical reaction. The solution was then standardised with sodium thiosulphate solution using starch indicator. Aqueous solution of glucose were prepared fresh each day. The solution of RuCl₃ and IrCl₃ (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in HCl solution of known strength. Acetic acid (AnalaR, Qualigen) was purified by standard method. Sulphuric acid (AnalaR) was used as source of [H⁺], potassium chloride (Merck) was used as source of [Cl⁻]. All other reagent were of analytical grade. Conductivity water used throughout the study.

Stoichiometry and molecularity of the reaction :

Stoichiometric studies were carried out under the conditions $[NBS] \gg [substrate]$. The reaction mixture containing $10^2 [NBS] = 5.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [substrate] = 5.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 [Hg(OAc)_2] = 7.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [H_2SO_4] = 1.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[AcOH] = 10\%$ (v/v) was kept for 36 h at 40 °C, the concentration of NBS was (after completion of the reaction) estimated at regular intervals of time (1 h) iodometrically using starch as indicator till the constant values were obtained. It has been observed that one mol of NBS, reacted with 1 mol of glucose in accordance with equation.

The product of oxidation of glucose were gluconic acid, the glucose were oxidised separately by NBr under kinetic conditions. The product thus obtained were purified, concentrated and then identified by paper chromatography. The paper chromatography⁵ was carried out with a descending solvent *n*-butanol (4) – acetic acid (1) – water (5) Whattmann filter paper no. 1 and identified with alkaline silver nitrate. Paper chromatography indicated the presence of aldonic acid with its corresponding δ -lactone in equilibrium.

The proposed mechanism is well supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters (Table 4). The high positive value of the energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and (ΔH^\ddagger) indicate that the transition state is highly solvated where as the negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) indicated that the activated complex is cyclic nature.

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References

1. N. Kambo and S. K. Upadhyay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1210; A. K. Singh, N. Gupta, S. Rahmani, V. K. Singh and B. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 187; Z. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 522.
2. A. L. Harihar, M. R. Kembhavi and S. T. Nandibewoor, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **76**, 128; B. Karimi, H. Seradj and G. R. Ebrahimiyan, *Synlett.*, 2000, 623; B. Das, J. Banerjee, N. Ravindranath and B. Venkataiah, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 2425; K. V. N. S. Srinivas and B. Das, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 1165; C. Ramesh, J. Banerjee, R. Pal and B. Das, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2003, **345**, 557; N. K. Mathur and C. K. Narang, "The Determination of Organic Compounds with *N*-Bromosuccinimide", Academic Press, New York, 1974; A. Shukla and S. K. Upadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 745; G. Thimme and J. Ishwara Bhat, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 211.
3. A. K. Singh, V. Singh, N. Gupta and B. Singh, *Carbohydr. PCS*, 2002, **337**, 345; M. R. Kembhavi, A. I. Harihar and S. T. Nandibewoor, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1999, **67**, 67; Puttaswamy, R. Ramchandrappa and N. M. M. Gowda, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1263; N. Grover, N. Kambo and S. K. Upadhyay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2482; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2002, **34**, 603; Mallama, S. Ananda, Rangaswamy and N. M. M. Gowda, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 250; N. Kambo and S. K. Upadhyay, *Trans. Met Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 461; N. Gupta, S. Rahmani and A. K. Singh, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1999, **22**, 237; G. A. Hiremath, P. L. Timmanagoudar and T. Nandibewoor, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **11**, 31; Z. Khan, M. Akram and Kabir-ud-Din, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1998, 460; Z. Khan, A. A. Hashmi and Kabir-ud-Din, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 147.
4. K. J. Laidler, "Chemical Kinetics", McGraw Hill, New York, 1965; S. G. Entelis and R. P. Tiger, "Reaction Kinetics in the Liquid Phase", Wiley, New York, 1976; P. S. Radha Krishna Murti and L. D. Sarangi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 30.
5. T. B. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, 1878.